

BUILDING SAFE SPACE FOR YOUTH (Media Ethnography in Reproductive Health Campaign at NTT through instagram @tenggarantt)

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ABSTRACT

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This research aims to understand the communication strategy of the adolescent reproductive health campaign conducted by the Tenggara Youth Community through a media ethnography approach. The main focus is on two campaign spaces: digital space (Instagram account @tenggarantt) and offline space (community activities in Kupang City and surrounding areas). Using Chris Heuer's 4Cs theory as an analytical framework-including context, communication, collaboration, and connection-the study found that Southeast's campaign strategy was contextual, inclusive, and participatory. Their digital content utilized local language and youth-friendly design, and used the hashtag #YouthCareYouthShare as a symbol of the campaign's core values. On the other hand, the offline approach through the Bacarita Kespro program managed to reach thousands of teenagers, including marginalized groups. This research concludes that a media-based community approach can effectively shape safe spaces and empower adolescents on reproductive health issues. The research also recommends media capacity building, access expansion, and strategic partnerships as further steps.

KEYWORDS:

reproductive health, media ethnography, digital campaign, community communication, Tenggara Youth Community.

1. INTRODUCTION

The adolescence period is an important transitional phase in human life characterized by biological, psychological, and social changes. One of the crucial aspects of this period is the understanding of reproductive health. However, this issue is still considered taboo in Indonesia, especially in formal spaces such as schools and families, so adolescents often have no access to accurate information. This opens up opportunities for the spread of myths and misinformation related to sexuality, which can result in negative impacts on adolescents physical and mental health.

In East Nusa Tenggara (NTT), taboos around sexuality are reinforced by social and cultural norms, which hinder adolescents access to comprehensive reproductive health information. Myths such as 1) the prohibition of shampooing during menstruation or 2) the assumption that menstrual blood is dirty blood are still widely circulated. This situation further strengthens the stigma against women's

bodies and weakens preventive education related to sexual violence and sexual health in general.

Data shows an increasing trend of sexual violence cases in NTT. According to SIMFONI PPA (2023), cases of sexual violence increased from 149 cases in 2018 to 429 in 2022. SAFEnet (2023) also recorded 254 complaints of Online Gender-Based Violence (GBV) in the region. In addition, around 29-31% of adolescents in NTT have had premarital sexual intercourse (PKBI & OTMI, 2015). The lack of understanding about reproductive health causes high vulnerability to early pregnancy, sexually transmitted diseases, and sexual violence.

Comprehensive reproductive health education is an urgent need for adolescents. Educational efforts have been made through adolescent posyandu and school-based programs, but are limited by cultural resistance and lack of approaches that are suitable for local contexts. Social media has emerged as a promising alternative space for information dissemination that is inclusive, interactive, and accessible at any time. Boyd (2014) mentions that social media is a new social arena where norms, identities and power interact with each other, while Yulianingsih et al. (2020) stated that social media is effective in disseminating reproductive health information and resolving myths.

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In the context of new media, digital platforms such as Instagram become democratic campaign channels, allowing anyone to produce and disseminate content. Jenkins (2006) refers to it as a participatory culture, while Shirky (2008) emphasizes the role of the internet in enabling organizations without formal structures to create social change. For this reason, this research examines collective efforts that combine reproductive health issues with digital spaces. In East Nusa Tenggara (NTT), issues of sexual and reproductive health, gender, and gender-based violence have become the concern of a number of locally-based communities, such as the Tenggara Youth Community, Lowewini, and PKBI NTT. The existence of these communities is important because they not only act as information providers, but also as agents of social change in the midst of limited access and high social stigma towards these sensitive issues.

One community that actively uses social media for reproductive health campaigns is the Tenggara Youth Community in Kupang City, NTT. Through the Instagram account @tenggarantt, this community develops programs such as 1) Bacarita Kespro and 2) Teman Bacarita which aim to construct taboos around sexuality and provide reproductive health education that is sensitive to local culture. The content uses local language, creative visual approaches, and prioritizes participation and collaboration with various partners, such as government institutions and marginalized communities.

Tenggara Youth Community not only provides information, but also creates a safe and inclusive space for youth to discuss and learn about reproductive health. Their digital campaign reflects how social media can be an effective health communication transformation tools, especially for the digital generation in areas with high social and cultural challenges. As part of its communication strategy, the community actively builds digital branding through various campaign hashtags, one of them is #YouthCareYouthShare. This hashtag reflects the spirit of solidarity and collaboration between teenagers in spreading reproductive health information. Through the use of this hashtag, Tenggara formed an identity as a community that not only cares, but also encourages teenagers to share knowledge and experiences in a participatory manner in the digital space.

To analyze the digital campaign practices carried out by this community, this research uses Chris Heuer's 4C (Context, Communication, Connection, Collaboration) theory. This theory offers a framework for understanding the dynamics of digital communication in the context of communities and social media. Through this approach, the research will examine how @tenggarantt builds a narrative context that is in accordance with local culture (context), strategically delivers educational messages (communication), builds relationships with their digital audience (connection), and collaborates with various social actors (collaboration) in

voicing reproductive health issues. Based on this background, this study aims to explore how reproductive health digital campaign practices are conducted by the Tenggara Youth Community through Instagram. This research uses a media ethnography approach to understand content production, interaction with audiences, and communication strategies used in building discourse around reproductive health that is contextual and culturally relevant.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach with a media ethnography method. The choice of this approach was chosen because it is able to deeply reveal communication practices, participatory culture, and the dynamics of social relations formed through digital media and offline interactions. The media ethnography method allows researchers to be actively involved in the social context in which the community operates, while observing the practice of media representation that takes place in the online space.

The research location is divided into two main spaces, namely online space and offline space. The online space focuses on the Instagram account @tenggarantt, which is managed by the Tenggara Youth Community as the main media in running their digital campaign. In this space, researchers conducted 1) observations of campaign content, 2) interactions between account managers and their followers, and 3) forms of digital communication practices displayed. Meanwhile, the offline space covers Kupang City and its surrounding areas, where the community's direct activities take place, such as discussions, educational campaigns, and face-to-face meetings between members.

In the data collection process, researchers used several techniques, namely participatory observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation. Observations were conducted intensively in both online and offline spaces to understand the context, interaction patterns, and activities of the community as a whole. In-depth interviews were conducted face-to-face with two key informants, namely Mariana Yunita Opat as the founder of the Tenggara Youth Community, and Ilta Tafuli as the community coordinator. The interviews were conducted in informal locations that were conducive to in-depth data exploration. In addition, documentation of visual materials, digital archives, as well as records of community activities and literature studies were also collected as part of the research data.

As a theoretical framework, this research uses the 4C theory developed by Chris Heuer, namely Context, Communication, Collaboration, and Connection. Heuer (2007) states that: "Social media is not about broadcasting; it is about conversing. The 4Cs - Context, Communication, Collaboration, and Connection - help us to move beyond traditional marketing paradigms and create value through shared meaning and mutual engagement." This statement emphasizes that social media should be understood not just as

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a channel for message distribution, but as a space for conversation and engagement. This theory is used to mapped how communities build social engagement, establish communication, collaborate on campaigns, and create connections between online and offline spaces. With this framework, the research seeks to comprehensively explain the communication dynamics that take place in digital communities and their social praxis.

III. RESULTS

This study aims to analyze the digital campaign on adolescent reproductive health by Tenggara Youth Community through the Instagram account @tenggarantt. Based on the results of digital observation and in-depth interviews, three main findings were obtained: (1) utilization of Instagram as a digital safe space, (2) participatory communication strategies through interactive content, and (3) integration of local cultural values in the campaign narrative.

The results showed that the Tenggara Youth Community actively utilizes social media, especially the Instagram account @tenggarantt to voice adolescent reproductive health issues strategically, consistently, and contextually. Through a down-to-earth communication approach based on community participation, their campaign is not only informative, but also transformative. The analysis of their media practices is mapped through the four pillars of Chris Heuer's 4C theory: Context, Communication, Collaboration, and Connection, which integrally show how this community builds meaningful digital spaces.

a. Context: Local Narratives and Cultural Sensitivity

Tenggara Youth Community demonstrates a strong understanding of context by raising reproductive health issues that are relevant to the needs of adolescents in NTT, such as menstruation, sexually transmitted infections, sexual violence, and healthy relationships. Their content shows a consistent and purposeful focus. Tenggara is presented in the midst of NTT society that still considers it "taboo" to talk about sexuality and reproductive health. This context encourages the community to create a safe space for teenagers to discuss these issues. One form of contextual expression that stands out is the use of non-formal language with the insertion of local terms such as "bacarita" and "dong". This narrative reinforces their identity as a local community that is close to NTT's youth audience, rather than simply copying the style of national campaigns. The presence of the hashtag #YouthCareYouthShare in every post is an important symbol in this context not only as a campaign marker, but also as a statement of values and movement direction. This hashtag creates a shared narrative that invites teenagers to be actively involved, care for each other, and share knowledge horizontally. In the context of NTT, which is known for its close-knit community-based social networks, this spirit of

collectivism is an important force in shaping meaningful digital engagement.

b. Communication: Visual Representation and Interactive Dialogue

In the digital realm, communication is no longer one-way, but open, dialogic, and participation-based (Jenkins, 2006). Tenggara Youth Community implements this principle through interactive and responsive content. They not only deliver information about reproductive health, but also open space for youth to share experiences, ask questions, and even contribute to content production.

According to Shirky (2008), the power of social media lies in its ability to encourage "mass amateurization," which is the involvement of audiences in the production of public discourse. This is reflected in features such as question boxes on Instagram Stories, polls, and community-run online discussion spaces. Tenggara's digital communication is horizontal, in accordance with the characteristics of networked publics (boyd, 2010), which allows for the formation of non-hierarchical social relationships between users.

The community utilizes various digital platforms such as Instagram, YouTube, websites and podcasts to deliver information and education to teenagers. They also hold live discussions through programs such as "Bacarita Kespro". Tenggara's visual content is in the form of educational carousel posts with a simple yet communicative design. The choice of warm colors and inclusive symbols creates a sense of safety and openness, very important for sensitive issues such as reproductive health. Captions are written in a conversational style that is easy to understand, signaling an empathetic and participatory communication strategy. Interestingly, although the quantitative engagement (likes and comments) is not high, the quality of the interaction is very deep. Audiences not only expressed support, but also shared their personal experiences, showing this account was successful in establishing a digital safe space. This is where #YouthCareYouthShare becomes more than just a slogan - it becomes a marker of the value of community communication that is open, empathetic and avoids stigma.

c. Collaboration: Collective Involvement and Content Co-production

Collaboration is an important foundation of contemporary digital media practices. As emphasized by Jenkins et al. (2013), collaboration in a participatory culture opens up opportunities for the creation of collective intelligence. Tenggara Youth Community implements this by involving teenagers as content co-creators, resource persons, and discussion facilitators, rather than just educational objects. The collaboration dimension is apparent in Tenggara Youth Community's engagement with other communities, both locally and nationally. They often tag partner communities, volunteers, and activity participants in their

posts, and collaborate with other accounts such as @kreatorkonten_cop, @unfpaindonesia @uninindonesia @youthcoalition_id. This not only expands the reach of the message, but also demonstrates an inclusive collaborative culture. This creates networked collaboration (Rainie & Wellman, 2012), strengthening message reach and expanding access to resources and authority. In the interview, Tata Yunita explained that they developed the Bacarita Kespro module with a locally-based and accessible approach, including for adolescents with deaf disabilities and those in remote areas. This collaboration strengthens the meaning of sharing in #YouthCareYouthShare, which is not only sharing information, but also sharing space and resources for social change. In the framework of digital communication, this kind of collaboration reflects produsage (Bruns, 2008), which is the combination of simultaneous production and use of information. Youth not only receive content, but also contribute to the shared narratives and knowledge that are formed collectively.

d. Connection: Safe Spaces and Digital Social Networks

Connection, refers to the ability of digital media to build social networks based on emotional closeness and solidarity. According to Papacharissi (2010), digital media create spaces where collective identities and feelings of community can be formed through affective communication practices. The Tenggara Youth Community embodies this through empathic narratives, peer support, and the spirit of “care culture” that they echo through hashtags such as #YouthCareYouthShare. The @tenggarantt account has built meaningful connections with its audience through emotional engagement and responsiveness to teens' information needs. Although their following is not large in number, the relationships built are close and trusting. Documentation of offline activities such as workshops and community discussions uploaded on Instagram serve as a bridge between online and offline spaces, reinforcing the continuity and presence of the community in real life. The hashtag #YouthCareYouthShare is not only present as a branding campaign, but as a value binder, an invitation to form a digital ecosystem that cares and shares. This is called a networked symbol that strengthens connections between teenagers (Zappavigna, 2012). It contains the values of inclusivity, mutual care, and the desire to grow with characteristics that strengthen emotional connections (Baym, 2010) between community members and audiences. Platforms like Instagram, with its commenting, DM and live session features, allow for more intimate and direct relationships. This reflects the transition from mass communication to personalized, emotionally connected communication evolution of digital communication that Castells (2012) has discussed in his network society theory.

Overall, Tenggara Youth Community's media

practices demonstrate that community-based digital campaigns can be effective and impactful when executed with cultural sensitivity, emotional immediacy, and collaborative communication strategies. The consistent use of the hashtag #YouthCareYouthShare not only marks the identity of the campaign, but also embodies the key values of the movement: caring, openness, and solidarity of youth across backgrounds.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study shows that the use of social media, especially Instagram, by the Tenggara Youth Community has shaped contextual, collaborative, and participatory digital campaign practices on adolescent reproductive health issues. This finding is in line with and at the same time extends the findings of previous studies that examine the use of social media in health and environmental issues.

Widarini's study (2019) highlighted the effectiveness of @aisyiyahpusat Instagram account in socializing information about reproductive health and nutrition for women. Using an Islamic value-based digital communication approach, the campaign prioritized the use of educational content such as infographics and live broadcasts. However, challenges that emerged in the study were the limitations in engaging the younger generation and the lack of adaptation to the local context. In this context, the Tenggara Youth Community approach actually shows strengthening in this aspect: narratives built through local languages such as “bacarita” and informal delivery styles are differentiating factors that make campaign messages more relevant and grounded in the eyes of NTT youth.

Meanwhile, research by Trisnayanti and Handaningtias (2024) through the #TemanLebihBaik campaign by Kalla Group on Instagram also used Chris Heuer's 4C theory as an analytical framework. The campaign emphasized environmental awareness through plastic reduction. Despite systematically applying the elements of context, communication, collaboration, and connection, the study noted that community involvement was still less than optimal, and not all elements of the communication strategy were executed optimally, for example the absence of collaboration with influencers or environmental activists who could potentially expand the campaign's reach.

In this context, the digital campaign by the Tenggara Youth Community not only applied the 4Cs theory fully, but also strengthened aspects of cross-sector collaboration and emotional connection with its audience. The involvement of marginalized communities, the development of modules with an accessible approach (including for youth with disabilities), and the use of typical greetings such as “bacarita friend” symbolize inclusivity and horizontal relations in their digital communication. This aspect complements the shortcomings found in the Kalla Group campaign study, which despite strong branding and content continuity, has not fully

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succeeded in building participatory and inclusive engagement (Trisnayanti & Handaningtias, 2024).

When compared, these three studies have similarities in using social media as an educational campaign tool, but differ in the context of the issue, target audience, and narrative approach. Widarini (2019) focused on adult women with a religious value approach; Trisnayanti and Handaningtias (2024) focused on environmental issues in a corporate context; while this study raised the issue of adolescent reproductive health in areas with minimal access to information. Of the three, the community-based approach and local culture by Tenggara proved to be the most powerful in building a safe and participatory digital space, as shown in the active involvement of the audience, co-production of content, and integration between online and offline spaces.

As such, these findings reinforce the understanding that digital campaigns are most effective when executed through culturally sensitive, participatory and community-based communication strategies. Social media does not only function as a channel for information distribution, but also as a space for social interaction that allows for changes in perception and behavior, especially in sensitive issues such as adolescent reproductive health.

In addition to the previous two studies, research by Patimoa, Mandaru, and Aslam (2022) on the Instagram account @kupang.foodies also provides an interesting picture of how social media is used in the local context of NTT. Although the focus is on halal culinary promotion, this study shows a strong two-way communication pattern between the account manager and followers, as well as the maximum use of social media features to create an emotional connection with the audience.

The study found that there are three types of communication effects that arise from digital content, namely cognitive, affective, and behavioral effects. This finding is in line with the findings of this study, where digital interactions on @tenggarantt's account not only generate new understanding (cognitive), but also trigger emotional engagement (affective) and even real participation in offline spaces (behavioral).

However, unlike @kupang.foodies which is oriented towards individualized and transactional promotion, @tenggarantt's campaign demonstrates a transformative community-based approach, especially in sensitive issues such as adolescent reproductive health. The @tenggarantt campaign also integrates online and offline spaces through activities such as Bacarita Kespro, and strategically builds narratives using local cultural symbols and the hashtag #YouthCareYouthShare as a marker of solidarity and a digital safe space.

By comparing these three studies Widarini (2019), Trisnayanti & Handaningtias (2024), and Patimoa et al. (2022) it appears that the effectiveness of digital campaigns is largely determined by: Local context and cultural

sensitivity, maximum utilization of social media features, and the ability to build emotional and participatory relationships with audiences. This research reinforces that social media is not only a medium for information dissemination, but also an arena for identity formation, community, and a strategic value negotiation space for social issues such as adolescent reproductive health.

Research by Ridwan and Sari (2023) on the creative process of interactive content on Instagram @majalahsunday enriches the understanding of the importance of content design strategies that are relevant to teenage audiences. Through the application of Graham Wallas' creativity theory, content creation is done systematically and collaboratively through the stages of preparation, incubation, illumination, and verification. The findings emphasize that creativity is not just an aesthetic aspect, but an important part of building emotional and cognitive interactions with adolescents, especially for sensitive issues such as mental health and sexuality.

Sunday magazine actively incorporates topics such as sex education and mental health into their interactive content such as polls, games, QnA, and vent sessions, which demonstrates the effectiveness of a light and friendly educational approach. This is parallel to the findings of this study on the @tenggarantt account, which also uses participatory and experiential content strategies of teenagers in NTT, to discuss reproductive health issues.

However, an important difference lies in the social dimension and locality. If Sunday focuses more on the production and branding process in urban areas (Jakarta), then the @tenggarantt campaign builds narratives based on marginalized communities with local cultural approaches such as "Bacarita". This provides a new contribution, that creativity is not only built from the production flow, but also from understanding the social context, culture, and community values.

By comparing these four studies Widarini (2019), Trisnayanti & Handaningtias (2024), Patimoa et al. (2022), and Ridwan & Sari (2023) it can be concluded that the effectiveness of digital campaigns in adolescent health issues is strongly influenced by:

1. Creative approach in content creation (production process),
2. Two-way and participatory communication strategies,
3. Sensitivity to cultural context and local issues, as well as
4. Success in building an emotional connection (engagement) with the audience.

The campaign by @tenggarantt, in this case, is a practice that combines all of these elements: creative in production, strong in communication strategy, and socially and culturally contextual.

V. CONCLUSION

This research shows that the Tenggara Youth Community has successfully designed and run a strategic

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adolescent reproductive health (SRH) campaign through the utilization of digital and offline spaces. By making the Instagram account @tenggarantt as the main space for digital campaigns, this community is able to present narratives that are focused, contextual, and inclusive. The media ethnography approach used in this research, with Chris Heuer's 4C theoretical framework (Context, Communication, Collaboration, and Connection), shows that their communication practices are not only informative, but also build meaningful social and cultural relations for teenagers in East Nusa Tenggara (NTT).

Contextually, their educational content consistently discusses SRH issues such as menstruation, sexual violence, healthy relationships, and rights-based sex education, while using typical NTT colloquialisms such as "bacarita" or "dong". This strategy not only strengthens the emotional connection with local audiences, but also shows sensitivity to the culture and identity of teenagers in the region. The simple yet communicative visuals of the content, as well as the selection of inclusive colors and symbols, create a sense of safe space for the audience. The hashtag #YouthCareYouthShare, which was consistently used, not only strengthened the campaign's branding, but also represented the core values they were building: youth care, participation and solidarity.

Although their accounts do not yet have a large number of followers, audience engagement shows a high quality of interaction and is participatory. Active replies to comments and direct messages, as well as audience encouragement to share personal experiences, show that this digital space has become an effective medium for two-way communication. In offline practice, campaigns such as Bacarita Kespro have successfully reached thousands of adolescents in the NTT region, including vulnerable groups such as adolescents with disabilities and indigenous communities, who were previously difficult to access reproductive health education

However, there are still a number of aspects that can be strengthened to improve the sustainability and reach of this campaign. First, increasing the capacity of digital content production in terms of design and visual narrative can expand the appeal and reach of audiences, including at the national level. Second, optimizing digital engagement strategies through interactive programs such as live sessions or user-generated content will strengthen audience participation. Third, expanding accessibility through alternative media such as community radio, WhatsApp, or printed materials is essential to reach youth in areas with limited internet access. Fourth, systematically documenting good practices and publishing campaign narratives can strengthen their position as innovative community campaign models. Last but not least, the expansion of strategic partnerships with schools, health facilities, and local stakeholders can broaden the impact and strengthen the sustainability of the program.

In this way, Southeast Youth Community has demonstrated that a community-based, culturally sensitive, and creatively utilized digital media reproductive health campaign can be a transformative force in assisting adolescents to deal with reproductive health issues in a critical and inclusive manner.

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